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DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL AND COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN ENGLISH OF MUSIC EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article highlights the relevance of developing professional communication skills in teaching English to students studying in the field of music education. Since the field of music requires active communication, research, creative exchange and international cooperation on a global scale, English is considered not only a general communicative tool, but also a professional necessity. The study analyzes ways to expand professional vocabulary in English, the correct use of musical terms in oral and written speech, and the formation of communication skills using interactive methods. Also, suggestions are made for the development of professional communication through role-playing games, dialogues, interviews, presentations and work with music texts in the lesson.

Keywords: music education, English, professional communication, communicative competence, interactive methods, language learning, music terminology.

Introduction.

In today's globalization process, the international integration of each sphere, in particular, art and education, is increasing. In particular, music, as a language without borders, the most subtle and powerful tool connecting peoples, cultures, and ideas, is gaining wide coverage worldwide. In such conditions, young people studying music should not only have a deep understanding of national culture, but also have the opportunity to bring it to the international arena, enrich it with foreign experience, and demonstrate their activities in a wide range. This directly requires the formation of professional communication skills in a foreign language, especially English. English is considered not only a general means of communication, but also an integral element of modern music education. Today, scientific articles on music, foreign methodological manuals, international seminars, Internet resources, modern technologies - all are conducted in English or provide access to this language. The effective use of these resources by the student, the ability to communicate freely with foreign colleagues, teachers or artists is a great professional advantage.

From this point of view, it is becoming an important task for students of music education to master the English language not only at the level of grammar or vocabulary memorization, but also to form communication skills that are suitable for their professional needs, that is, used in creative, musical and pedagogical activities. This process should be based on modern, interactive and communicative approaches. It is necessary to create a thorough methodological foundation so that students can use

English in real-life situations, express their musical ideas, discuss, make presentations, and participate in international projects. This article analyzes in detail this urgent issue - ways, methods and pedagogical approaches to developing professional communication skills in English of students of music education. This not only increases the efficiency of the educational process, but also increases the ability of students to think independently and conduct their professional activities at an international level.

For students studying music education, learning English is important not only as a means of developing language competence, but also as a means of expanding their professional growth and opportunities for entering the international arena. In particular, the development of professional communication skills in this process is one of the most urgent tasks. However, as a result of insufficient attention to this area in traditional teaching processes, many students have difficulty applying their knowledge in practice. Therefore, English teachers are seeking new methodological solutions based on modern, innovative and interactive approaches.

Professional communication refers to the student's ability to effectively use the terminology, expression styles, question-and-answer methods, and intercultural communication in English. In the field of music, this allows you to describe musical works, express your creative vision, participate in international conferences, review foreign literature, or exchange ideas with foreign teachers.

To develop such skills, first of all, it is necessary to use professionally oriented texts in the learning process. For example, lessons based on the lives of famous composers, music genres, analysis of works, concert reviews, or articles on musical technologies increase students' interest in the language and bring them closer to professional activities. Through these materials, students not only increase their vocabulary, but also learn to consistently express their thoughts about music in English. Also, lessons based on role-playing games and musical interviews are an important tool for strengthening communication skills. For example, through roles such as “composer and journalist”, “concert host and listener”, “teacher and student”, students model real-life professional situations in English. This serves not only to learn grammar, but also to strengthen their speaking style. In addition, preparing and presenting presentations teaches students to think independently, search for information and convey it to the audience in an effective way. By preparing a presentation in English about a musical work, composer, or national musical tradition, not only professional knowledge is deepened, but also a culture of oratory and communication is formed.

Another effective method is to learn a language using online resources. In particular, through music lessons on YouTube, TED Talks, podcasts, or international music forums, students hear live English, immerse themselves in a professional environment, and master the language in a natural context.

It is worth noting that English teachers should also organize lessons taking into account the specifics of the music industry. Interpreting, translating, and comparing musical terminology, aesthetic means of expression, and the language of musical thought in English — these processes lead to the professionalization of the pedagogical approach. The formation of professional communication skills in English is not only a language study, but also a comprehensive process aimed at developing musical thinking and a professional worldview in an international context. Through this, students in the music field are formed as modern, competitive and socially active specialists.

Literature analysis:

The issue of teaching English in a professional direction has been considered one of the most relevant topics in the education system in recent years. Especially in specialized areas such as music education, teaching a foreign language shows the need to form, in addition to general language competence, communication skills that are directly related to professional activity.

In this direction, A. Khodjaev emphasizes in his research that teaching English based on a communicative approach is very effective in increasing students' speech activity. He especially notes the importance of involving students in active speech activity through interactive methods - discussion, dialogue, role-playing games, presentations. These methods are also suitable for developing the skills of music education students to participate in professional communication.

Among the foreign literature, D. Dudley-Evans and T. St John's "Developments in English for Specific Purposes" covers the methodological foundations of English lessons with a professional focus. The authors justify the need to create language resources, tasks and communication forms suitable for each field of study through the concept of ESP (English for Specific Purposes). This approach can also serve as the basis for developing individual methodologies for the music field.

Local authors E. Mamatova studied the possibilities of using English in music education and emphasized the need to develop dictionaries, textbooks, listening comprehension materials, and translation practices based on music terminology. Her research serves to deepen musical thinking along with language learning.

Also, J. Harmer's "The Practice of English Language Teaching" is an important guide to general language teaching methodology. It provides important recommendations for the effective use of modern technologies, multimedia tools, and interactive platforms in English lessons. Lessons integrated into music subjects can be organized based on such approaches.

Regarding the relationship between language and music, American researcher P. J. Hickey studied the cognitive aspects of music and language learning and proved that language materials associated with music (for example, songs, musical texts) serve to

improve memory, pronunciation, and increase motivation for the language through emotional impact.

Another noteworthy aspect is the relevance of teaching language through materials based on musical themes in international testing systems (for example, IELTS, TOEFL). Through these tests, students strengthen not only general language skills, but also professional and cultural literacy.

In general, the analyzed literature shows the importance of the following main approaches in teaching English in the field of music:

Professional orientation: Language materials should be selected in accordance with the field of music;

Communicative methods: It is important to involve students in active communication;

Interactive and multimedia tools: Resources that enrich the teaching process are necessary;

International experience: Adaptation to the local system based on foreign methodological literature;

Cross-disciplinary approach: Integrated education by creating a connection between music and language.

Discussion:

The issue of forming professional communication skills in English of students studying in the field of music education is not only a pedagogical task within the narrow scope of language teaching, but also an important factor ensuring the competitiveness of future specialists in the international labor market. In today's globalized era, characterized by rapid information exchange, English serves as a platform for international dialogue, scientific cooperation, musical experience and news. Especially for young people working in the field of art and culture, the need to be able to communicate freely in this language, express professional ideas and cooperate on an equal basis with foreign colleagues is increasing day by day.

Practical observations show that among students studying music, there is an interest in communicating in English, but in order to fully satisfy this need, the content and methodology of classes are more focused on general language skills. The curricula do not sufficiently provide for work with professional terminology, musical texts, and articles on international musical art. This situation limits students to theoretical language knowledge and deprives them of the opportunity to express their opinions in real professional situations, participate in creative projects, and enter into musical dialogue with foreign colleagues.

As a solution to this problem, the idea of integrating English with music education is being put forward. This means that English should serve the student's professional growth as a part of music education, not just a general language lesson. For example,

during the lesson, working with materials in English about the lives of famous composers, work analyses, musical genres, explaining musical terms, making presentations in English and organizing debates ensures the student's dual development: it simultaneously enriches language and professional competencies. Also, the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies into the language learning process, in particular the use of interactive platforms, audiovisual materials, music podcasts and online forums, creates an environment of lively communication among students. They express their opinions about the work they are listening to, write music criticism or conduct questions and answers in the form of interviews. Such activities bring the student to the level of "using" the language, not "learning".

In addition, when teaching English, it is also important to form in students' minds the idea that "language is not a test, but a creative tool." Not being afraid of learning a language, but rather considering it as a convenient tool for their musical expression, increases the student's motivation. In this sense, experiences in writing, translating, and even composing songs in English can also yield effective results. During the research process, it became clear that the development of professional communication skills in English plays a decisive role in expanding the creative, professional, and intellectual potential of students in the field of music education. In this regard, it is possible to achieve greater effectiveness through systematic, integrated, and student-oriented educational and methodological approaches. After all, language is not just knowledge, but also an opportunity. Especially in the field of art, this opportunity serves as the key to finding one's place on the global stage.

Conclusion.

The art of music is one of the most subtle and inspiring manifestations of human thought, and it is valued as a means of communication that is deeper than language. However, in today's era of globalization, this art is gaining even wider coverage through language, especially through English. From this perspective, the ability of students studying music education to communicate professionally in English should be recognized as an important skill that ensures their professional maturity, creative potential, and active participation in the international arena. Based on the conducted analysis and literary sources, it can be said that teaching English in an integrated manner with music education not only forms language competence, but also educates the student as a stronger professional specialist. Through such an approach, he will not only master grammatical rules, but also have the opportunity to express his creative ideas to a foreign audience, develop professional contacts, and actively participate in global musical processes. It has also been proven that interactive methods, multimedia tools, tasks close to real life, and working with texts based on musical terminology are very effective in developing professional communication skills. In particular, classes based on free exchange of ideas in a creative environment increase the student's interest

in the language and prepare him for practical speech. In conclusion, it can be said that interpreting English not only as a separate subject, but also as an indispensable tool for musical creativity and pedagogical activity is a requirement of modern education. This approach creates opportunities for students to think independently, communicate freely, find their place in the professional arena, and cooperate equally with musical cultures around the world. After all, today's music teacher is not only a modern creative person who teaches musical instruments, but also communicates with the world through English.

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